

LEADERSHIP CULTURE-THE KEY TO ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract. *Spirituality of a leader is formed (internal) spiritual strength of a leader. His spiritual psychological culture is a set of emotional knowledge that is valued at the level of value based on the example of ancestors, regulates the spiritual world of a person, and reaches the level of skill. In order for the leader to improve his leadership potential, it is necessary to acquire knowledge that enriches his spiritual world and to increase his ability to initiate. Knowledge, which has become the spiritual property of the leader, helps him to limit his desires and protect himself from external pressures and influences.*

Keywords: *new Uzbekistan, leadership culture, appearance, behavior, spirituality, speech culture, organization, productivity.*

Introduction. Spirituality of a leader is the formed (internal) spiritual strength of a leader. His spiritual psychological culture is a set of emotional knowledge that is valued at the level of value based on the example of ancestors, regulates the spiritual world of a person, and reaches the level of skill. In order for the leader to improve his leadership potential, it is necessary to acquire knowledge that enriches his spiritual world and to increase his ability to initiate. Knowledge, which has become the spiritual property of the leader, helps him to limit his desires and protect himself from external pressures and influences. That is, to be a morally perfect leader is to be able to control oneself in any socio-psychological environment, to be satisfied with creating a healthy environment in the team one leads and among the general public, and to treat people sincerely. A leader with a high morale can show will, courage and activity in the fight against evil, injustice, lawlessness in the society, actions against the interests of the Motherland. A leader who has thoroughly mastered psychological knowledge embodies high-level standards of culture, behavior, and ethics. This requires the leader to improve his individual and intellectual level in every way. The experience gained on the path of independent development, the path of unique development recognized by the world community as Uzbek model, and all the historical changes and updates that are being implemented to build a great country in the future will greatly help to fundamentally change the personal beliefs and spiritual image of the leaders. A leader who can clearly imagine his leadership activity, the goals he has set for himself, and who cares for the future, cannot develop without a national idea and spiritual ideology in any era. Any leader who does not have a spiritual image and a spiritual ideology will lose his way. Whichever society has a more spiritually mature leader, historical progress and recovery in this community will take place without sharp political "shocks", social "pains" and economic "shocks". From a moral point of view, it is easy for a leader with a strong mind to take the big road with personnel and to positively solve all the problems facing the people and the nation.

Research Methodology. Leaders can be divided into several categories in terms of the level of spiritual and psychological culture:

1. Leaders with a relatively low moral level. Such leaders are devoid of simple moral and spiritual qualities, they do not understand the moral standards of the society and they do not respect them.

2. Leaders who have a low level of moral culture and morals, and who destroy the psychological environment related to public opinion, family, folk traditions and other values.

3. Leaders who blindly accept moral standards without internal conviction and feeling as a vital necessity. Such leaders have high theoretical knowledge, but in practice they cannot apply this knowledge or they lack organizational skills.

4. Leaders who are spiritually weak and have a high moral culture, but perceive injustice with a sharp emotion. They have enough moral knowledge, but they lack initiative, independence and courage to show it.

5. Enterprising, enthusiastic leaders who have sufficient knowledge of spiritual culture and political-psychological knowledge. They are rich in deep knowledge, deep thinking and sharp observation, spiritual feelings. Of course, the role of young leaders is invaluable in the fact that our country is entering the Third Renaissance and the countries of the world are becoming more interested in studying our New Uzbekistan. The formation and development of the leader's spirituality is usually manifested in three components.

The first link in the form of ideology is information, gathering information, mainly expressed at the level of words, opinions, examples, ideas and theories. The leader gets to know the spiritual heritage, values, assimilates them, integrates the newness into his worldview. This is a link of trust. The second link is cultural and spiritual views, moral values, traditions, and religious and spiritual feelings instilled in a person from a young age. In this link, he feels unity with his family, relatives, neighborhood, and nation. As a result, a sense of national pride and patriotism is formed in his mind and heart. This link is the link of faith. For this reason, our ancestors put forward the idea that "loving the country is a matter of faith." The third syllable is represented by knowledge, creative research, understanding. It appears in our thinking in the form of enlightenment, worldly spirituality. Our great scholars perfected this worldly spirituality in harmony with divine spirituality.

If the first link is receiving news, the second is relying on values, the spirit of ancestors, then the third link is the creative development of news. It is a true heir to the heritage of ancestors, and it implies the creative development of their valuable part. It is necessary to restore national values, glorify the spirituality left by the ancestors, learn from it, and realize one's identity. After all, any destructive idea can affect a person who is poor in spirituality, who does not have his own independent outlook and opinion.

The tomorrow of our Uzbekistan will be people who are morally and culturally mature, mentally fresh, have the ability to think and work independently, who have professional skills that meet the requirements of the scientific and technical development of their time, who have high pride, full of faith, strong will, truly patriotic, honest and noble people.

Conclusion. All elements of management culture are interrelated and interacting. At the same time, among them, the culture of management personnel is of leading importance. The manager must achieve a high level of culture of the management process and improve the organization of his work. For this, the leader must constantly critically analyze his work and continuously improve the leadership culture.

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